

Supplementary figure 2. Multiplex cytokine measurement in brain at 6 h, 1 d, 3 d, 7 d and 14 d after neonatal hypoxia-ischemia or sham operation. Values are pg/mg protein and presented as the mean $\pm$ SD. The statistical results are presented in supplementary table 1.